

Critical Analysis of Wheat Bran as Therapeutic Source

Manali Chakraborty¹, Dr Savita Budhwar²

¹PhD Scholar, ²Assistant Professor

^{1,2}Department of Nutrition Biology, Central University of Haryana, Mohindergarh, Haryana, India

How to cite this paper: Manali Chakraborty | Dr Savita Budhwar "Critical Analysis of Wheat Bran as Therapeutic Source" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-3 | Issue-3, April 2019, pp.296-303, URL: <http://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd21755.pdf>

IJTSRD21755

Copyright © 2019 by author(s) and International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development Journal. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0) (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>)

ABSTRACT

Increasing population now-a-days is one of the most crucial phases of upcoming future troubles. Food wastage along with the nutritional expenditure should not be entertained. Several milling by-products of crops viz., wheat bran, are principle pool of nutrients. It is very much essential to study and gain knowledge about the nutrients, anti-oxidants, anti-nutritional components and their effect upon diseased condition along with the probability of production of edible food stuffs for human. Though there is enough production of wheat bran, most of the amount is either wasted or used as livestock fed. It has been shown that bran part has potential efficiency to be used as therapeutic tool for various diseases such as, cancer, obesity and diabetes, bowel irritation etc. Its role as a prebiotic might also prove an asset to remarkably influence gut microflora. Its anti-nutritional content is also lower than the rice bran and that is also manageable for the further use as food stuff. The physicochemical properties along with its nutrient as well as anti-nutrient contents must be utilized and regulated as requirement to combat malnourishment besides hunger issues and therapies.

Keywords: wheat bran, by-products, nutrient content, physicochemical property, phytic acid

1. INTRODUCTION

Global population and its subsequent increment is one of the most critical challenges for the future. Additional food demand, malnourished condition would create a terrible concern in the coming timeline of human kind until and unless maintenance of post-harvest losses and food security is considered from now only. It is expected that population mark will rise up to 9.1 billion people by the year 2050 and almost 70% extra food requirement will be needed to avoid hunger issues¹⁻³. Though developing countries already started to improve their agricultural condition and productions, awareness regarding post-harvest loss (PHL) is still not sufficient. Less than 5% research funding has been issued in this context in previous few years⁴⁻⁷. "Food loss" is defined as food that is available for human consumption but goes unconsumed^{8,9}. Not only the post harvest losses are required to come across our concern, agro wastes from milling industries are also come under vital issues. Due to lack of proper knowledge, less research on human consumption, these milling by-products are only used either for animals or a very lesser amount as human fed. Although these are being used for industrial purposes, nutritional importance of these wasted by-products are also matter to be noticed. "Food waste" is described as discarded food or alternatively the intentional non-food use of the food or due to spoilage/expiration of food¹⁰. These wasted by-products, mainly husk, straw, bran or broken parts of many cereals, pulses if processed carefully and efficiently, production of cheap and nutritious foodstuffs might be possible. Most

consumed and popular food crops in the World mainly are cereal grains viz., wheat, which are also the foundation of staple foods in most of the budding countries. Maintaining loss of these cereals besides the utilization of every part of these grains could be one of the proficient ways to combat hunger, food demand, malnourish, and rural development. Wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) comprises its bran part (13-19%) that is mainly used for nonfood purposes in spite of having high nutrient significance. Only 10% bran is being used in food industries^{11,12} among 45 to 90 million tons worldwide production (FAO 2011). It is highly rich in phytochemicals and minerals along with dietary fiber. Consumption of bran already been linked to reduced risk in cancer, diabetes, cardiovascular diseases due to presence of biochemical compounds entrenched in it¹³.

2. Production of wheat and its bran:

Reducing agro losses during industrial processing and to make use of by-products appropriately for human feed is now a major global concern. Before utilizing such wasted parts, their nutrient as well as anti-nutrient breakdown is very much needed to understand for their consumable properties along with toxicities, if any. It is also crucial to gather data about their physicochemical properties that helps in many aspects of food product formation.

Besides rice paddy, wheat is also a primary cereal crop, mainly used for human consumption and domestic animals

feed. Among its principle fractions, bran is mostly used. According to GAIN (Global Agricultural Information Network) report (IN7031), marketing year 2017/18 wheat production is 95 MMT from 31.8 million hectare and about 3.0 MT/hectare yield. The major by-product from flour milling i.e. bran is mainly used for animal fed. 90% bran is utilized for this purpose and rest 10% for food products wasting rich nutrients¹².

Figure 1: Percentage of wheat grain parts¹⁴

Micro contents present in wheat bran:

Nutrient analysis as well as anti-nutrient estimation of the agro wastes is very much urgent to know about their delicate properties and also harmful characteristics, if any¹⁵.

Especially the outer layer of wheat grain contains high level of antioxidants, vitamins (vit-E, B), phenolic compounds, sterols, minerals, insoluble dietary fibers. Its nutritional composition also includes bioactive compounds viz. alkyl rescorcinols, ferulic acid, flavonoids, carotenoids, lignans, also called phytochemicals^{11,13, 16}. Phenolic acids in bran part remain in bound and free, both states with approximately 99% of ferulic acid in insoluble and bound situation¹⁷.

Table 1: Nutritional breakdown of wheat bran:

Major components of bran portion ¹⁷	
Bran component	Range % dm
Dietary fiber	33.4-63.0
Moisture	8.1-12.7
Ash	3.9-8.10
Protein	9.60-18.6
Total carbohydrate	60.0-75.0
Starch	9.10-38.9
Phytochemicals	µg g⁻¹
Alkylrescorcinol	489-1429
Phytosterols	344-2050
Ferulic acid	1376-1918
Bound phenolic compound	4.73-2020
Flavonoids	3000-4300
Micronutrients	Mg per 100 g
Phosphorus	900-1500
Magnesium	530-1030
Zinc	8.3-14.0
Iron	1.9-34.0
Manganese	0.9-10.1
Vitamin E (Tocopherols/ tocotrienol)	0.13-9.5
Vitamin B	
Thiamin (B1)	0.51-1.6
Riboflavin (B2)	0.20-0.80
Pyridoxine (B6)	0.30-1.30
Folate (B9)	0.088-0.80
Other essential components in wheat bran¹⁸	
Components	g/100g wheat bran
a) Non-starch polysaccharide	
Glucan	10.5
Xylan	18.3
Arabinan	10.1
Galactan	1.1
b) Starch	34.0
c) Klason lignin	5.0
d) Crude protein	13.5

Antioxidants in bran		
Antioxidant	Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{ g}$)	Reference
Lignans		
lignan aglycones	2774	19
Syringaresinol	1953	
Isolariciresinol	297	
Lariciresinol	257	
Secoisolariciresinol	142	
pinoresinol	106	
matairesinol	9.4	
Carotenoids	0.68	20
Lutein	1.8	
Zeaxanthin	0.54–27	
Tocopherols		
α tocopherols,	1.28–21.29	21
δ tocopherols,	0.23–7.0	
γ tocopherols,	0.92–6.90	

Note: Dm, dry matter.

Due to presence of these potential components in wheat bran it could be beneficial to lower blood cholesterol level, cardiovascular diseases, type II diabetes, cancer prevention and many others^{18,22}

Table 2: Presence of nutrition in various part of wheat bran layers:

Wheat bran layer	Nutrient	Reference
The pericarp	Insoluble dietary fiber Ferulic acid Bioactive compounds Vitamins	23
Aleurone layer	Minerals Vitamin B Protein Lignans Bioactive compounds Antioxidant Phytate Phenolic acids	24-29
Testa tissue	Alkylrescorcinols	30

High amount of starch as well as nitrogen content in wheat bran in comparison to that of rice, it can be used as an inducer for the production of various enzymes viz., CMCase, amylase, phytase etc³¹⁻³⁴.

Besides, wheat bran is been used for several metabolite production such as Bacitracin by *Bacillus licheniformis* along with soya bean in 1 : 3³⁵.

Table 3: list of enzymes, present in wheat bran:

Enzymes	Producer microorganism	Enzyme activity	Reference
Proteases			
	Aspergillus sp. and Mucor pusilus	--	36
Acid Protease	Aspergillus oryzae	--	37,38
Neutral metallo protease	Aspergillus oryzae NRRL 2217	--	39
Acidic	Aspergillus oryzae MTCC 5431	8.26×10^5 U/g cell mass	34
Alkaline	Thermoactinomyces thalophilus PEE14	1620 U/g cell mass	40
α-amylase			
	Bacillus licheniformis	--	41
	Bacillus cereus MTCC 1305	122 U/g cell mass	42
	Aspergillus niger	-	43
	Apergillus awamori: Nakzawa MTCC 6652	9420 U/g cell mass	44

Lipase	Aspergillus niger	4.8 IU/ml	45
	Bacillus megatarium AKG1	--	46
	Alkalophilic Yeast		47
Pectinase	Streptomyces lydicus	--	48
	Bacillus sp. DT7	8050 IU/g cell mass	49
	Aspergillus niger	36.3 IU/g cell mass	50
	Penicillium veridicaltum RFC3	100 IU/ml	51
	Aspergillus foetidus NRRL 341	1860 IU/g cell mass	52
Glucoamylase	Aspergillus HA-2	264 U/g cell mass	53
	Aspergillus sp.	454 U/g cell mass	54
	Aspergillus oryzae	1986 U/g cell mass	55
Xylanase	Aspergillus niger	33%	56
	Trichoderma longibrachiatum	592.7 U/g cell mass	57
	Bacillus sp. AR009	720 U/g cell mass	58
	Bacillus licheniformis A99	1.63 U/g cell mass	59
	Aspergillus niger XY-1	14637 U/g cell mass	60
	Staphylococcus sp. SG-13	4525 U/l	61
Cellulase	Trichoderma reesei RUT C30	--	62
	T. viride CMGB	3.18 FPU/ml	63
Tannase	Paecilomyces variotii	--	64
	Aspergillus aculeatus DBF9	8.4 U/g cell mass	65

Table 4: effects of fermentation on the antinutritional factors (tannins and phytic acid)⁶⁶

wheat bran	Tannin (mg catechin/ 100 gm material)	Phytic acid (mg/100g)
non-fermented		
Coarse	0.03 ^d	626.12 ^c
Medium	0.06 ^b	740.36 ^b
Fine	0.07 ^a	795.20 ^a
Fermented		
Coarse	0.01 ^e	572.79 ^d
Medium	0.05 ^c	367.13 ^e
Fine	0.06 ^b	301.63 ^f

3. Physicochemical properties of bran:

In a study the particle size was reduced to 90 µm from 1200 µm along with hydrothermal (wet steeping in acetate buffer at pH 4.8 at 55 °C for 60 min) and fermentation (using bakery yeast for 8 h at 30 °C) to note down the effect of these combined treatments upon few properties of bran with a goal to reduce phytic acid content, an anti-nutrient, of the bran. Though Hydrothermal and fermentation decreased, particle size reduction on its own or in combination increased bran lightness. Decrease in swelling power along with water solubility and water holding capacity was observed with reduction in particle size. Although Swelling power and water holding capacity of the hydrothermalead and fermented bran were lesser, in reverse, water solubility was elevated than the control. The amount of Fe⁺², Zn⁺² and Ca⁺² were also become less when the particle size was reduced. Interestingly fermentation had no hit upon Fe⁺²and Zn⁺² but somewhat reduced Ca⁺² were recorded. The hydrothermal behavior to some extent lowered these elements' level. Hydrothermal treatment by the side of particle size reduction showed the lowest phytic acid and maximum fiber content⁶⁷. Physiological effects of insoluble dietary fibers are also been get influenced due to the physicochemical properties during consumption. Thus it points out that these properties should be customized to get better the fibers' physiological properties. Treatment with microfluidization process of the bran was done to analyze effects on physicochemical properties. This treatment showed that this process could successfully reduce particle size and bulk density, and significantly enlarge specific surface area, water-holding capacity, swelling capacity, oil-holding capacity and cation-exchange capacity. These nutritionally related changes may boost the physiological properties of bran^{68,69}. To increase the value of wheat bran further than livestock feed needs an ample set of methodical tools. This review gives an outline over the breakdown of wheat bran constituents in general and dietary fiber in particular with a spotlight on instrumental techniques. Gas chromatography, liquid chromatography, capillary electrophoresis, thin layer chromatography, size-exclusion chromatography, field-flow fractionation, nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy and infrared along with near-infrared spectroscopy are accessible for dietary fiber analysis⁷⁰.

Table 5: Sources of wheat bran as human fed⁷¹:

Product	Fibre per 100 g AOAC	Standard portion size (g)	Fiber per portion (g)
Bran shreds breakfast cereal	27	40	10.8
Bran flakes breakfast cereal;	15	30	4.5
Shredded wheat breakfast cereal	11.8	45	5.3
Extruded pillos breakfast cereal	9.9	45	4.5
Whole wheat biscuits breakfast cereal	10	37.5	3.8
Wholemeal bread	7362.5		
Granary bread	5.3	36	1.9
Brown bread	5361.8		
Sliced white bread	2.5	36	0.9
Dried whole meal pasta (uncooked weight) 9	44	4.0	-----
Dried wholemeal pasta (uncooked weight) 9	87	7.8	-----
Dried wholemeal pasta (uncooked weight) 9	130	11.7	-----
Dried white pasta (uncooked weight)	2.8	75	2.1
White pasta (cooked weight)	1.2	180	2.2
Wheat couscous (dry weight)	5603.0	-----	-----

Note: Compiled from Manufacturer's websites 2011.

4. Wheat bran and diseases:

Wheat bran plays a key role in case of bowel cancer. According to the European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition (EPIC)⁷² people who take low fiber diet can appreciably lessen risk of colorectal cancer, by 40%, due to intake of more fiber-rich foods. Likewise, the World Cancer Research Fund's report on cancer and diet, physical activity and weight recommended that foods containing fiber decline risk of colorectal cancer (WCRF/AICR 2007). In addition, animal studies have also confirmed a noteworthy defensive outcome of wheat bran on colon carcinogenesis in rats fed a high-fat western-style diet⁷³. Wheat bran, together with psyllium (50:50), resulted in enhanced shield and synergistic effects may hold back various phases of the carcinogenic process, besides wheat bran phytic acid slow down earlier stages and psyllium restrain later stages⁷⁴. Colon cancer is not the only cancer which is linked to fiber. A notable shielding effect of fibre also observed in breast cancer research. According to⁷⁵ in pre-menopausal women, total fiber acts like shield against breast cancer, in particular fiber from cereals and possibly fruit.

Cardiovascular diseases also get benefit from whole grains when it contains considerable amount of fiber or bran. A major effect on CVD had been noticed leading to reduction in level of serum cholesterol. Consumption of a wheat bran-based breakfast cereal for 3 weeks, containing roughly 13.5 g of fiber, serum cholesterol was dropped down from 5.576 to 4.385 mmol/l in those participants with the highest quintile of serum cholesterol according to a study done by⁷⁶ Costabile et al. Besides, no decline was noted in beneficial HDL-C, signifying beneficial effects on CVD risk. Carlson et al.⁷⁷ found that increasing dietary fibre was associated with lower risk of metabolic syndrome coronary heart disease (CHD).

Data from epidemiological studies confirms a contrary connection between ingestion of dietary fiber and weight gain and obesity, while fiber utilization is allied with enhanced satiety and less energy intake⁷⁸. Along with these it is also recorded that dietary fiber amplifies faecal energy loss⁷⁹. The consequence of wheat bran on postprandial appetite regulating hormones is not that much well studied, though a recent animal study⁸⁰ found out the effect of wheat bran on GLP-1 secretion, and no effect on body weight,

adipose tissue mass, glucose or insulin resistance was observed. On the other hand, this work displayed a hit of wheat bran on inflammation, together with decreased inflammatory cytokines.

McIntyre et al.⁸¹ showed wheat bran has an effect on faecal bulking along with delayed gastric emptying and accelerated small bowel transfer. Dietary intake may modify the gut flora components such as having prebiotic. Prebiotics are as non-digestible food ingredients that constructively have an effect on host health by selectively stimulating the growth and/or activity of one or a limited number of bacteria in the colon⁸². Prebiotic contents of dietary fiber in wheat bran (including beta-glucans) due to fermentation by colonic microflora form SCFA, which results in physiological changes to the colonic contents, leading to change in bulking, water retention capacity and viscosity. Costabile et al.⁷⁶ found a more unassuming alter in gut microflora after having a wheat bran cereal, rather than a whole grain cereal. Markers of colonic metabolic output (including ferulic acid and SCFAs) also get more than before.

5. Conclusion:

Each year a large amount of wheat bran are wasted in spite of possessing significant nutritional quality. Though bran is used for livestock fed, biodegradable material packaging and as human fed in some extent, it has not been that much utilized due to lack of analytical tools and techniques. More detailed studies and project plan should be proposed to beneficially use up the bran to slow down the nutritional wastage.

Reference:

- [1] Godfray H.C.J, Beddington J.R., Crute I.R., Haddad L, Lawrence D, Muir J.F., Pretty J, Robinson S, Thomas S.M and Toulmin C. Food security: The challenge of feeding 9 billion people. Science. 327: 812–818 (2010).
- [2] Hodges R.J, Buzby J.C. and Bennett B. Postharvest losses and waste in developed and less developed countries: Opportunities to improve resource use. J. Agric. Sci. 149: 37–45 (2011).
- [3] Parfitt J., Barthel M. and Macnaughton S. Food waste within food supply chains: Quantification and potential

- for change to 2050. *Philos. Trans. R. Soc. B Biol. Sci.* 365: 3065–3081 (2010).
- [4] Bourne M. Post Harvest Food Losses—the Neglected Dimension in Increasing the World Food Supply; Department of Food Science and Technology, Cornell University: Ithaca, NY, USA (1977).
- [5] Greeley M. Food, Technology and employment: The fram-level post-harvest system in developing countries. *J. Agric. Econ.* 37: 333–347 (1986).
- [6] Kitinoja L., Saran S., Roy S.K. and Kader A.A. Postharvest technology for developing countries: Challenges and opportunities in research, outreach and advocacy. *J. Sci. Food Agric.* 91: 597–603 (2011).
- [7] Pantenius C. Storage losses in traditional maize granaries in Togo. *Int. J. Trop. Insect Sci.* 9: 725–735 (1988).
- [8] Aulakh J., Regmi A., Fulton J.R. and Alexander C. Estimating post-harvest food losses: Developing a consistent global estimation framework. In Proceedings of the Agricultural & Applied Economics Association's 2013 AAEA & CAES Joint Annual Meeting, Washington, DC, USA, (2013).
- [9] Buzby J.C., Farah-Wells H. and Hyman, J. The estimated amount, value, and calories of postharvest food losses at the retail and consumer levels in the United States. Available online: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2501659 (accessed on 31 May 2015).
- [10] Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations. Global Initiative on Food Losses and Waste Reduction; FAO: Rome, Italy, 2014.
- [11] Aprich S., Tirpanalan O. and Hell J. € et al. Wheat bran-based biorefinery 2: valorisation of products. *LWT-Food Science and Technology.* 56: 222–231 (2013).
- [12] Hossain K., Ulven C. and Glover K. et al. Interdependence of cultivar and environment on fibre composition in wheat bran. *Australian Journal of Crop Science.* 7: 525–53 (2013).
- [13] Andersson A.A.M., Dimberg L., Aman P. and Landberg, D. Recent findings on certain bioactive components in whole grain wheat and rye. *Journal Cereal Science.* 59: 294–311 (2014).
- [14] Surget A. and Barron, C. Histologie du grain de ble. *Industrie des Cereales.* 145: 3–7 (2005).
- [15] Chakraborty M, Budhwar S, Pooja, Vinod. Nutritional and therapeutic value of rice bran. *IJGHC.*, 7: 451-461 (2018).
- [16] De Brier N., Gomand S.V., Joye I.J., Pareyt B., Courtin C.M. and Delcour J.A. The impact of pearling as a treatment prior to wheat roller milling on the texture and structure of bran-rich breakfast flakes. *LWT-Food Science and Technology.* 62: 668–674 (2014).
- [17] Lu Y., Luthria D., Fuerst E.P., Kiszonas A.M., Yu L. and Morris, C.F. Effect of processing on phenolic composition of dough and bread fractions made from refined and wholewheat flour of three wheat varieties. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry,* 62: 10431–10436 (2014).
- [18] Javed M.M., Zahoor S. and Shafaat, S. et al. Wheat bran as a brown gold: nutritious value and its biotechnological applications. *African Journal of Microbiology Research.* 6: 724–733 (2012).
- [19] Begum A.N., Nicolle C., Mila I., Lapierre C., Nagano K., Fukushima K., Heinonen S.M., Adlercreutz, H. Remesy and C. Scalbert, A. Dietary lignins are precursors of mammalian lignans in rats. *J. Nutr.* 134: 120–127 (2004).
- [20] Adom K.K., Sorrells M.E. and Liu R.H. Phytochemical profiles and antioxidant activity of wheat varieties. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 51: 7825–7834 (2003).
- [21] Zhou K. and Yu L. Antioxidant properties of bran extracts from Trego wheat grown at different locations. *J. Agric. Food Chem.* 52: 1112–1117 (2004).
- [22] Wang J., Smits E., Boom R.M. and Schutyser M.A.I. Arabinoxylans concentrates from wheat bran by electrostatic separation. *Journal of Food Engineering.* 155: 29–36 (2015).
- [23] Hemery Y., Rouau X., Lullien-Pellerin V., Barron C. and Abecassis J. Dry processes to develop wheat fractions and products with enhanced nutritional quality. *J. Cereal Sci.* 46: 327–347 (2007).
- [24] Pomeranz Y. *Wheat, Chemistry and Technology.* Am. Assoc. Cereal Chem. St. Paul, MN (1988).
- [25] Antoine C., Lullien-Pellerin V., Abecassis J. and Rouau X. Nutritional interest of the wheat seed aleurone layer. *Sci. Aliment.* 22: 545–556 (2002).
- [26] Rhodes D.I. and Stone B.A. Proteins in walls of wheat aleurone cells. *J. Cereal Sci.* 36: 83–101 (2002).
- [27] Buri R.C., von Reding W. and Gavin M.H. Description and characterization of wheat aleurone. *Cereal Food World.* 49: 274–282 (2004).
- [28] Slavin J.L., Martini M.C., Jacobs D.R. and Marquar L. Plausible mechanisms for the protectiveness of whole grains. *Am. J. Clin. Nutr.* 70: 459S–463S (1999).
- [29] Esposito F., Arlotti G., Bonifati A.M., Napolitano A., Vitale, D. and Fogliano V. Antioxidant activity and dietary fibre in durum wheat bran byproducts. *Food Res. Int.* 38: 1167–1173 (2005).
- [30] Landberg R., Kamal-Eldin A., Salmenkallio-Marttila M., Rousset M. and Aman P. Localization of alkylresorcinols in wheat, rye and barley kernels. *J. Cereal Sci.* 48: 401–406 (2008).
- [31] Maheswari M.U. and Chandra T.S. Production and potential applications of a xylanase from a new strain of *Streptomyces cupidosporus*. *World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol.* 16: 257–263 (2000).
- [32] Sindhu R., Suprabha G.N. and Shashidhar S. Optimization of process parameters for the production of alpha amylase from *Penicillium janthinellum* (NCIM 4960) under solid state fermentation. *Afr. J. Microbiol. Res.* 3(9): 498–503 (2009).
- [33] Soarse F.E.F., Braga F.R., Genier H.L.A., Araujo J.V., Ferreira S.R., Aaujo J.M., Tavela A de O, Vilela V.L.R. and Queiróz J.H. Optimization of medium composition for protease production by *Paecilomyces marquandii* in solid-state-fermentation using response surface

- methodology. Afr. J. Microbiol. Res. 4(24): 2699-2703 (2010).
- [34] Vishwanatha, K.S., Appu Rao A.G. and Singh S.A. Acid protease production by solid-state fermentation using *Aspergillus oryzae* MTCC 5341: optimization of process parameters. J. Ind. Microbiol. Biotechnol. 85: 1849-1859 (2009).
- [35] Farzana K., Shah S.N.H., Butt F.B. and Awan S.B. Biosynthesis of bacitracin in solid-state fermentation by *Bacillus licheniformis* using defatted oil seed cakes as substrate. Pak. J. Pharm. Sci. 18: 55-57 (2005).
- [36] Sumantha A., Larroche C. and Pandey A. Microbiology and industrial biotechnology of food-grade proteases. Food Technol. Biotechnol. 44: 211-220 (2006).
- [37] Tsujita Y. and Endo A. Purification and characterization of the two molecular forms of *Aspergillus oryzae* acid protease. Biochim. Biophys. Acta. 445: 194-204 (1976).
- [38] Sandhya C., Sumantha A., Szakacs G. and Pandey A. Comparative evaluation of neutral protease production by *Aspergillus oryzae* in submerged and solid-state fermentation. Process Biochem. 40: 2689-2694 (2005).
- [39] Sumantha A., Sandhya C., Szakacs G., Soccol C.R. and Pandey A. Production and partial purification of a neutral metalloprotease by fungal mixed substrate fermentation. Food Technol. Biotechnol. 43: 313-331 (2005).
- [40] Divakar G., Sunitha M., Vasu P., Udaya shanker P. and Ellaiah P. Optimization of process parameters for alkaline protease production under solid state fermentation by *Thermoactinomyces thalophilus* PEE14. J. Biotechnol. 5: 80-83 (2004).
- [41] kram-ul-Haq Ashraf H., Iqbal J. and Qadeer M.A. Production of alpha amylase by *Bacillus licheniformis* using an economical medium. Bioresource Technol. 87: 57-61 (2003).
- [42] Anto H., Trivedi U. and Patel K. Alpha Amylase Production by *Bacillus cereus* MTCC 1305 using solid-state fermentation. Food Technol. Biotechnol. 44: 241-245 (2006a).
- [43] Kaur P., Grewal H.S and Kocher G.S. Production of α -amylase by *Aspergillus niger* using wheat bran in submerged and solid state fermentations. Indian J. Microbiol. 43: 143-145 (2003).
- [44] Negi S. and Banerjee R. Amylase and protease production from *A. awamori*. Food Technol. Biotechnol. 44: 257-261 (2006).
- [45] Falony G., Armas C.J., Mendoza D. and Hernandez M.L.J. Production of extracellular lipase from *Aspergillus niger* by solid state fermentation. Food Technol. Biotechnol. 44: 235-240 (2006).
- [46] Sekhon A., Dahia N., Tewari R.P. and Hoondal G.S. Production of lipase from *Bacillus megaterium* AKG-1 using wheat bran in solid substrate fermentation. Indian J. Microbiol. 44: 219-220 (2004).
- [47] Bhushan B., Dosanjh N.S., Kumar K. and Hoondal G.S. Lipase production from alkalophilic yeast by solid state fermentation. Biotechnol. Lett. 16: 841-842 (1994).
- [48] Jacob N. and Prema P. Pectinases from Actinomycetes. Food Technol. Biotechnol. 44: 263-267 (2006).
- [49] Kashyap D.R., Soni S.K. and Tewari R. Enhanced production of pectinase by *Bacillus* sp. DT7 using solid state fermentation. Bioresource Technol. 88: 251-254 (2003).
- [50] Debing J., Peijun L., Stagnitti F., Xianzhe X. and Li L. Pectinase production by solid fermentation from *Aspergillus niger* by a new prescription experiment. Ecotoxicol. Environ. Saf. 64: 244-250 (2006).
- [51] Silva D., Tokuioshi K., da Silva Martins E., Da Silva R. and Gomes E. Production of pectinase by solid-state fermentation with *Penicillium viridicatum* RFC3. Process Biochem. 40: 2885-2889 (2005).
- [52] Cavalitto S.F., Jorge A.A. and Hours R.A. Pectinase production profile of *Aspergillus foetidus* in solid state cultures at different acidities. Biotechnol. Lett. 18: 251-256 (1996).
- [53] Anto H., Trivedi U.B. and Patel K.C. Glucoamylase production by solid-state fermentation using rice flake manufacturing waste products as substrate. Bioresource Technol. 97: 1161-1166 (2006b).
- [54] Ellaiah P., Adinarayana K., Bhavani Y., Padmaja P. and Srinivasulu B. Optimization of process parameters for glucoamylase production under solid state fermentation by a newly isolated *Aspergillus* species. Process Biochem. 38: 615-620 (2002).
- [55] Zambare V. Solid State Fermentation of *Aspergillus oryzae* for glucoamylase production on Agro residues. Int. J. Life Sci. 4: 16-25 (2010).
- [56] Dobrev G.T., Pishtiyski I.G., Stanchev V.S. and Mircheva R. Optimization of nutrient medium containing agricultural wastes for xylanase production by *Aspergillus niger* B03 using optimal composite experimental design. Bioresource Technol. 98: 2671-2678 (2007).
- [57] Azin M., Moravej R. and Zareh D. Production of xylanase by *Trichoderma longibrachiatum* on a mixture of wheat bran and wheat straw: Optimization of culture condition by Taguchi method. Enzyme Microb. Tech. 40: 801-805 (2007).
- [58] Gessesse A. and Mamo G. High-level xylanase production by an alkaliphilic *Bacillus* sp. by using solid-state fermentation. Enzyme Microb. Tech. 25: 68-72 (1999).
- [59] Archana A. and Satyanarayana T. Xylanase production by thermophilic *Bacillus licheniformis* A99 in solid-state fermentation. Enzyme Microb. Tech. 21: 12-17 (1997).
- [60] Xu Y.X., Li Y. L., Xu S.C., Liu Y., Wang X. and Tang J.W. Improvement of xylanase production by *Aspergillus niger* XY-1 using response surface methodology for optimizing the medium composition. J. Zhejiang Univ. Sci. B. 9: 558-566 (2008).
- [61] Gupta S., Kuhad R.C., Bhushan B. and Hoondal G.S. Improved xylanase production from a haloalkalophilic *Staphylococcus* sp. SG- 13 using inexpensive agricultural residues. World J. Microbiol. Biotechnol. 17: 5-8 (2001).

- [62] Sukumaran R.K., Singhania R.R., Mathew G.M. and Pandey A. Cellulase production using biomass feed stock and its application in lignocellulose saccharification for bio-ethanol production. *Renew. Energ.* 34: 421-424 (2009).
- [63] Vintila T., Dragomirescu M., Jurcoane S., Caprita R. and Maniu M. Production of cellulase by submerge and solid state cultures and yeasts selection for conversion of lignocellulose to ethanol. *Rom. Biotechnol. Lett.* 14: 4275-4281 (2009).
- [64] Battestin V. and Macedo G.A. Tannase production by *Paecilomyces variotii*. *Bioresource Technol.* 98: 1832-1837 (2007).
- [65] Banerjee D., Mondal K.C. and Pati B.R. Tannase production by *Aspergillus aculeatus* DBF9 through solid-state fermentation. *Acta Microbiol. Hung.* 54: 159-166 (2007).
- [66] Hassan E.G., Alkareem A.M.A. and Mustafa A.M.I. Effect of Fermentation and Particle Size of Wheat Bran on the Antinutritional Factors and Bread Quality. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition.* 7 (4): 521-526 (2008).
- [67] Majzoobi M., Pashangeh S., Farahnaky A., Eskandari M.H. and Jamalian J. Effect of particle size reduction, hydrothermal and fermentation treatments on phytic acid content and some physicochemical properties of wheat bran. *J Food Sci Technol.* 51(10): 2755-2761 (2014).
- [68] Guillon F. and Champ M. Structural and physical properties of dietary fibres, and consequences of processing on human physiology. *Food Research International.* 33: 233-245 (2000).
- [69] Wang T., Sun X., Zhou Z. and Chen G. Effects of microfluidization process on physicochemical properties of wheat bran. *Food Research International.* 48: 742-747 (2012).
- [70] Hell J., Kneifel W., Rosenau T. and Bohmdorfer S. Analytical techniques for the elucidation of wheat bran constituents and their structural features with emphasis on dietary fiber-A review. *Trends in Food Science & Technology.* 35: 102-113 (2014).
- [71] Stevenson L., Phillips F., Kathryn o'Sullivan and Walton J. Wheat bran: its composition and benefits to health, a European perspective. *International Journal of Food Sciences and Nutrition.* 63(8): 1001-1013 (2012).
- [72] Bingham S.A., Day N.E. and Luben R. Dietary fibre in food and protection against colorectal cancer in the European Prospective Investigation into Cancer and Nutrition (EPIC): an observational study. *Lancet.* 361:1496-1501 (2003).
- [73] Alabaster O., Tang Z. and Shivapurkar N. Dietary fibre and the chemopreventive modulation of colon carcinogenesis. *Mutat Res.* 350:185-197 (1996).
- [74] Alabaster O., Tang Z., Frost A. and Shivapurkar N. Potential synergism between wheat bran and psyllium: enhanced inhibition of colon cancer. *Cancer Lett.* 75:53-58 (1993).
- [75] Cade J.E., Burley V.J. and Greenwood D.C. Dietary fibre and risk of breast cancer in the UK Women's Cohort Study. *Int J Epidemiol.* 36(2):431-438 (2007).
- [76] Costabile A., Klinder A., Fava F., Napolitano A., Fogliano V. and Leonard C. Wholegrain wheat breakfast cereal has a prebiotic effect on the human gut microbiota. *Br J Nutr.* 99: 110-120 (2008).
- [77] Carlson J.J., Eisenmann J.C., Norman G.J., Oritz K.A. and Young P.C. Dietary fibre and nutrient density are inversely associated with metabolic syndrome in US adolescents. *J Am Diet Assoc.* 111: 1688-1695 (2011).
- [78] Freeland K.R., Anderson G.H. and Wolever T.M.S.. Acute effects of dietary fibre and glycaemic carbohydrate on appetite and food intake in healthy males. *Appetite.* 52: 58-64 (2009).
- [79] Astrup A., Kristensen N.T., Gregersen A., Belza A., Lorenzen J.K., Due A. and Larsen T.M. Can bioactive foods affect obesity. *Ann NY Acad Sci.* 1190: 25-41 (2010).
- [80] Neyrinck A.M., de Backer F., Cani P., Bindels L.B., Stroobants A., Portelle D. and Delzenne N.M. Immunomodulatory properties of two wheat bran fractions - aleurone enriched and crude fractions - in obese mice. *Int Immunopharmacol.* 8: 1423-1432 (2008).
- [81] McIntyre A.R.M., Vincent A.C., Perkins R.C. and Spiller R.C. Effect of bran, ispaghula, and inert plastic particles on gastric emptying and small bowel transit in humans: the role of physical McIntyre factors. *Gut.* 40:223-227 (1997).
- [82] Gibson G.R. and Roberfroid M.B. Dietary modulation of the human colonic microbiota: introducing the concept of prebiotics. *J Nutr.* 125:1401-1412 (1995).